

<p>PHOTONICS PUBLIC PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP</p>	HORIZON 2020 FOF-13-DT6-Ares(2017)04957-72	HIPERLAM GA No: 723879
	Document Owner:	TNO
	Author:	Gari Arutinov
HiperLAM Deliverable Report	PUB	V4

D3.1: The selection of materials based on the inputs of the coating and the LIFT printing experiments

Dissemination Level: Public (PUB)

Owner

Lead Beneficiary: TNO

Work Package: WP3, High speed, High Volume AM Laser Printing Process

Related Task T3.1: Pre-selection of materials for LIFT printing

Author(s): Gari Arutinov

Co - Author(s): Jonathan Ankri (ORBK), Ioanna Zergioti (NTUA), Ayala Kabla (PV NanoCell), Semyon Melamed (PV NanoCell)

Phone: +31404020621

E-mail: gari.arutinov@tno.nl

D3.1 - The selection of materials based on the inputs of the coating and the LIFT printing experiments - Deliverable Report

PUB

V4

Version History

Ver.	Summary of Change	Written By	Approver	Date
1	1 st Draft	TNO		18.10.2017
2	2 nd Draft after feedback from PV NanoCell	TNO, PV Nanocell		28.10.2017
3	3 rd Draft after comment from ORBK	TNO, PV Nanocell, ORBK		31.10.2017
4	4 th draft after final comment from MODUS	TNO, PV Nanocell, ORBK		24.11.2017

Contents

Version History	2
1 Scope of Document	4
2 List of abbreviations	4
3 Iterative material selection process	4
3.1 The first round of ink evaluation	4
3.1.1 Donor layer quality	5
3.1.2 Jetability	6
3.1.3 Printability	6
3.2 The second round of ink evaluation	7
4 Conclusions.....	8

1 Scope of Document

HiperLAM is an SME driven Research and Innovation Action (RIA) well-aligned to the Factories of the Future (FoF) Initiative with a strong emphasis upon demonstrating superior cost and speed performance in end-to-end processes featuring laser-based additive manufacturing in two key applications requiring high resolution printed conductive metallic lines. Application 1 – laser printed RFID antenna. Application 2 - laser printed Fingerprint sensors. The promise of HiperLAM's high resolution laser based additive manufacturing solutions is to transform the manufacturing processing speed by 10x for laser printed RFID antenna and 5x in the case of the lead-time for laser printed fingerprint sensor design. Similarly, HiperLAM promises to reduce costs by 20x and 50% respectively for Application 1 and Application 2. The purpose of this document is to provide an overview of iterative screening and selection process of materials provided by the material developer of the consortium, PV NanoCell, based on the experimental studies conducted by respective laser-induced forward transfer (LIFT) printing partners, ORBK, TNO and NTUA.

Feedback on this document should be sent to Gari Arutinov: gari.arutinov@tno.nl

2 List of abbreviations

LIFT	Laser Induced Forward Transfer
np-ink	nanoparticle ink
ML	metal load
WP	Work Package
PET	Polyethylene terephthalate

3 Iterative material selection process

This deliverable describes the task of selecting suitable materials for LIFT printing through an iterative process that starts with a preliminary selection of materials from the commercial and R&D portfolio of PV NanoCell. Two rounds of ink supply were provided by PV Nanocell, where the first was prepared according to initial requirements defined by printing partners and the second set of materials with material properties tuned according to the detailed screening of the first round of inks. Of course, during the ongoing implementation of Work Package 2 (WP2) materials will be further fine-tuned according to LIFT performance characterization feedback from partners in order to meet corresponding end-user requirements.

3.1 The first round of ink evaluation

A first set of inks were prepared based on specifications defined by LIFT printing partners – NTUA, TNO and ORBK. For initial screening in total 12 silver np-inks were prepared by PV NanoCell. Silver nanoparticles with two different metal load (ML) content were suspended and stabilized in six

different solvents having a range of different properties, in particular varying in surface tension. The chosen six solvents are known to disperse the silver particles without causing agglomeration or sedimentation, therefore ensuring stability of prepared inks. In the first set of ink evaluation, screening of inks was conducted by experimental partners paying particular attention to donor layer quality, jettability and printability of provided np-inks.

3.1.1 Donor layer quality

For the LIFT technology, it's necessary to deposit the ink (including the functional particles) on the donor substrate. The quality of the film greatly influences the performance of the technology and properties that can be achieved. Therefore, before performing any printing experiment it is crucial to define the film quality parameters and their measuring methodology.

It is known that rheological properties of the ink, mainly defined by ML, host solvent and additives, have a major influence on the quality of the film. The different deposition methods are considered employed in the project aiming to deposit donor layers with desired uniformity, not exceeding in average 5% variation in layer film thickness across the whole layer.

In order to evaluate the applicability of provided 12 inks in terms of donor film quality, thin films of various thicknesses were applied using prism coating and characterized by TNO and ORBK using confocal microscope and interferometry-based 3D microscope, respectively. Acquired experimental data revealed a strong correlation between donor film quality and silver ML across all 12 np-inks. Due to a low viscosity of suspensions upon coating, the inks internal flows were vividly observed leading to uneven and irreproducible donor layers (Error! Reference source not found.). This behaviour was traced for all tested materials independent of the host solvent, indicating the need to increase the ink viscosity in next iteration rounds of material development.

Although none of the tested inks led to donor layers with desired uniformity and reproducibility, vivid improvement in donor quality was observed while using material with higher ML (Error! Reference source not found.).

Figure 1. Wet donor films applied with bar coating using two inks varying only in ML content, showing donor layers with (a) poor uniformity applied from an ink with low ML and (b) smoother (however still with visible internal flows) donor layer applied with the same ink with higher ML (TNO).

3.1.2 Jetability

Jetting behavior of provided inks were accessed through a visualization system available at NTUA. Using an ultrafast camera ejected jet were recorded and thoroughly analyzed.

Figure 2. Time-resolved images of LIFT printing of silver ink from a 35µm-thick donor film (NTUA).

Figure 2 illustrates a typical time-resolved images extracted from a recording of LIFT printing of silver ink. Jetting analysis revealed no significant difference in jetting behavior among provided inks. For all 12 formulations continuous jet were detected. Furthermore, NTUA through visualization inspection system has confirmed that vertical jets could be injected from donor films of various thickness (Figure 3 Error! Reference source not found.), thereby confirming the wide operating window for provided np-based formulations.

Figure 3. LIFT jets ejected from np-ink based donor films of various thickness (NTUA).

3.1.3 Printability

Upon confirming by NTUA jetability of provided inks (see section 3.1.2), LIFT printing performance of the materials has been evaluated by ORBK and TNO using glass and polyethylene terephthalate (PET) dummy substrates as test receiving carriers. For this set of tests 6 inks with the same ML content but suspended in 6 different solvents were selected. Based on donor evaluation tests (see section 3.1.1) inks with higher ML content were chosen as they led to more reliable and reproducible results. Laser parameters and printing strategies have been separately optimized for all 6 np-inks aiming to print an array of continuous lines on dummy substrates. Figure 4 illustrates an array of the lines deposited with corresponding optimized print strategies on PET substrate, pointing out to a significant difference in

printing performance of np-inks with the same ML depending on which host solvent nanoparticles are suspended in.

Figure 4. LIFT printed lines deposited on a PET substrate with optimized laser parameters using 35 μ m-thick donor films from six silver np-ink having same ML content and six different host solvents (a)-(f) showing a significant difference in printing performance depending on a host solvent nanoparticles are suspended in (TN0).

3.2 The second round of ink evaluation

Based on outcome of screening 12 inks provided in the first round, PV NanoCell prepared for the second round of ink evaluation two formulations based on two solvents that led to the best printing performance (Figure 4) and with the highest possible ML still preserving stability of the ink without introducing agglomerates and sedimentation. Donor coating of both inks led to uniform and reproducible donor layers (Figure 5) with no internal flows being evident in films applied with a first batch of materials.

	HORIZON 2020 FOF-13-2016	HIPERLAM GA No. 723879
<i>D3.1 - The selection of materials based on the inputs of the coating and the LIFT printing experiments - Deliverable Report</i>	PUB	V4

Figure 5. Wet donor films applied using inks with high ML suspended in two solvents that led to the best printing performance in the first iteration round showing smooth and consistent donor layers (TNO).

Laser parameters and printing strategies have been separately optimized for both np-inks and using these optimized printing parameters an array of continuous lines were printed on a dummy PET substrate (Figure 6).

Figure 6. An array of continuous LIFT printed lines deposited on a PET substrate with optimized laser parameters using np-inks with high metal load.

4 Conclusions

The content of this report provides an overview of iterative screening and selection process of materials provided by the material developer of the consortium, PV NanoCell, based on the experimental studies conducted by respective laser-induced forward transfer (LIFT) printing partners – ORBK, TNO and NTUA. In a two-step iterative process in total 14 inks were screened and evaluated in terms of donor layer quality, jettability and printability. A first set of inks were prepared based on specifications defined by LIFT printing partners. For initial screening in total 12 silver np-inks suspended were prepared by PV NanoCell. Silver nanoparticles with two different ML content were suspended and stabilized in six different solvents having a range of different properties. Firstly, donor coating experiments revealed the need to increase the ML content in inks in order to improve the uniformity and reproducibility of donor layers. Secondly, printing experiments aiming to investigate the dependence of printing performance on which host solvent silver nanoparticles were suspended in; out of 6 solvents selected by the consortium for the initial tests, two solvents showing the most reliable LIFT printing were selected for the second round of ink evaluation. Therefore, two inks suspended in the selected two solvents with higher ML content were prepared by PV NanoCell for the second round of ink evaluation. With both of these inks, uniform and reproducible donor layers were applied allowing to LIFT print an array of continuous lines on dummy PET substrates.

END OF DOCUMENT